

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

Authors:

Jule Hildmann (PhD); Senior Research Fellow in Outdoor Learning; The University of Edinburgh, UK; jule.hildmann@ed.ac.uk;

Pete Higgins (PhD); Professor/Chair in Outdoor Environmental & Sustainability Education, UK; The University of Edinburgh; Pete.higgins@ed.ac.uk

Simon White; Operations Manager; The Venture Trust, UK; Simon@venturetrust.org.uk

Mike Strang; Chief Operating Officer; The Venture Trust, UK; Mike@venturetrust.org.uk

Andy Hardie; Clinical Manager; The Venture Trust, UK; Andy.hardie@venturetrust.org.uk

Abstract

Background: Outdoor Adventure Education programmes have been argued to have the potential to nurture *empowerment* and *transformative competencies* that enable individuals and societies to navigate the global challenges of the 21st century towards shared prosperity, peace, and ecological sustainability by means of *transformative learning* experiences in the outdoors. To date, there is little specific guidance on how to achieve this on a practical facilitation level. **Purpose:** This paper presents a model on how to maximise empowerment and transformative competencies in wilderness experience programmes. **Methodology/Approach:** The model consists of the three main phases *Preparation*, *Exploration*, and *(Re)Integration* that are each composed of distinct factors of impact. The phases are woven together by three underlying principles of *Empowerment*, a *Nurturing ground for growth*, and specific *Facilitation strategies* such as situational micro-learning and safe space. **Findings/Conclusions:** Research and literature evidence the effectiveness of the model in promoting core components of transformative competencies in different target groups. Current data provide guidance for the adaptation of the model to new socio-cultural contexts. **Implications:** The model provides clear, evidence-based guidance for practitioners and program designers to facilitate transformative wilderness experiences to promote empowerment and transformative competencies in a range of populations.

Key words

Empowerment, transformative learning, transformative competencies, socio-emotional learning, facilitation, model

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

1. Context

'Transformation' - in the sense of transformative learning (after Mezirow, 1978) - means that a fundamental personal change takes place, in particular an evolution of beliefs, attitudes and perspectives that serve as a frame of reference for our thoughts, feelings and actions (Mezirow, 2018). Transformative learning is a concept from adult education built on the understanding that relevant experiences can lead us to question our previous frames of reference and update and expand them through dialectical meaning-making in interaction with our environment (Merriam, 2018; Mezirow, 2018; MacKeracher, 2012). Such changes of perspective have an emancipatory and socio-political component, since according to Fenwick (2003) and Lange (2012) the transformation does not take place in the individual alone, but in and through systemic relationships and interactions and their growth-provoking effects on the social system and its subsystems.

1.1 Transformative competencies

in connection to formal educational, the OECD (2019) conclude from research three *Transformative Competencies* (TC) argued to enable (young) people to master the social and ecological challenges of the 21st century, to transform our society and to create a sustainable and 'better future' (OECD, 2019, 2). The three TCs are: to

- Create new value
- Reconcile tensions and dilemmas
- Take responsibility

They are a further development of earlier 'key competences' (OECD, 2005) and are higher-level, complex competencies that are useful in diverse situations, for all social groups and over the entire lifespan (OECD, 2019; Rychen & Salganik, 2003). Therefore, they are seen as widely transferable (ibid. ; ibid.), UNESCO (2015) present a related list of competencies under the term 'transversal competences'.

The international research on which the definition of the key and transformative competencies is based (see DeSeCo project) emphasized that the competencies sought are not only of individual importance - "for a successful life" (OECD, 2005, 4; Rychen & Salganik, 2003) characterized e.g. by economic resources, political rights and influence, health, social networks and personal satisfaction and value orientation (Gilomen, 2003) - but also "for a well-functioning society" (OECD, 2005, 4; Gilomen, 2003, 128; Rychen & Salganik, 2003, title), which is characterized, among other things, by economic productivity, democratic processes, solidarity and human rights (Gilomen, 2003). As a third dimension of importance of the competencies, ecological sustainability is emphasized, as well as the interdependencies of the three dimensions (ibid.).

In detail, the three TCs are composed of a number of components, such as

- To critically reflect on one's own actions and attitudes
- To work together with others
- To consider the short and long-term effects of one's actions and to take responsibility for them
- To weigh up personal with ethical and social goals
- To be able to withstand tensions and contradictions and to try to resolve them with empathy and respect
- To put new insights into practice
- To respect our planet

(Compiled from OECD, 2019a).

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

Rickinson and colleagues (2004) as well as other authors refer to the development of transferrable socio-emotional competencies as *Socio-Emotional Learning* (SEL). The model presented in this paper uses relevant findings from research in outdoor and adventure education to promote the listed components of TCs / SEL through facilitated wilderness experiences.

1.2 Empowerment

Empowerment plays a central role in modern socio-political education and can be understood both as an educational goal and approach.

1.2.1 Empowerment as a goal

To be 'empowered' as a person means that they (a) feel they can bring about social, political, economic and other changes in their own situation and environment (Broom, 2015, 80; Cattaneo & Chapman, 2010), and (b) they take actual steps to exert such influence (Cattaneo & Chapman, 2010). Without explicitly referring to TCs, Broom (2015, 81) names several of the components listed under 1.1 in their definition of empowered individuals. Broom affirms that empowerment is of great importance for both individuals and society, and emphasizes that being empowered and actively contributing to one's own world (i.e. citizenship) is at the same time a personal right and duty, and nothing less than "the core of democracy" (ibid.).

A close connection between empowerment, SEL and TCs is widely agreed on: Several socio-emotional factors are understood as foundation for TCs (e. B. Rickinson et al. 2004; Cason & Gillis, 1994; Wilson & Lipsey, 2000) and the outward expression of empowerment in terms of social participation (Shellman, 2014). These are primarily:

- A healthy self-image and self-esteem (Baumeister et al. 2003; Allison & Von Wald, 2010)
- Sense of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997; Chen, Gully & Eden, 2004)
- Action-oriented components (i.e. behavior patterns, skills and abilities) of transformative competencies (see 1.1)

Depending on the target group and the specific event, these can be complemented by

- Subject-specific knowledge and technical skills, e.g. for the job market or practical life skills

1.2.2 Empowerment as a process

Empowerment is understood as a reiterative process of interactions with our social and more-than-human environment, which nurtures the aforementioned competencies (Cattaneo & Chapman, 2010).

1.2.3 Empowerment, Transformative Competencies, and Outdoor Experiential Learning

Facilitated wilderness experiences are widely agreed to be effective and appropriate in achieving personal and social transformation (Allison & Von Wald, 2010; Lloyd, 2018) that leads learners to build TCs (OECD, 2019). Shellman (2014) conducted a comparison of empowerment literature within outdoor education contexts. They convincingly concluded that 'experiential' practices that – like the model presented in this paper – "provide opportunities for participants to develop and master skills, participate in decision-making, receive feedback on behaviour, and view effort as an important contributor for outcomes" (ibid., 23) are "in several ways, aptly designed to empower [and are] perhaps the most effective means through which learners may develop a sense of empowerment" (ibid, 19). In line with this, the Federal Association of Person-centred and Experiential Education (Bundesverband Individual- und Erlebnispädagogik e.V.; based in central Europe) emphasizes the socio-political potential outdoor and adventure education holds, and the resulting responsibility for outdoor leaders (be, 2020).

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

One way to achieve empowerment as a process and objective, leading to the development of TCs, through outdoor and experiential learning is the model presented hereafter. The facilitation strategies to achieve this are embedded in its structure and outlined below.

2. The Edinburgh Model – Background and objectives

The model presented here builds on established insights from research in outdoor and experiential learning to promote SEL and TCs through facilitated wilderness experiences. It has been evaluated and refined over many years of practical implementation. The model is designed for SEL within *educational* group settings, with some key elements are gleaned from common therapeutic practice, such as 'immersion in an unfamiliar environment, group-living with peers, individual and group (...) sessions, educational curricula and application of (...) skills such as fire-making and backcountry travel' (Russell, Hendee & Phillips-Miller, 2000, p. 207).

2.1 Background

The Edinburgh Model was conceived in Scotland, UK, in collaboration between the Venture Trust (a national charity specialising in outdoor development work with a range of populations) and the department of Outdoor Environmental Education at The University of Edinburgh (UoE). The combination of decades of practical experience of Venture Trust and the research and academic expertise of the UoE staff established the base for the creation of the model.

2.2 Objectives

The overarching objective of the Edinburgh Model is the acquisition and exercise of TCs by program participants in order to achieve their personal goals as well as to promote citizenship.

Under this overarching objective, specific key outcomes that lead to empowerment are an increase in the program participants' socio-emotional learning, particularly:

- Sense of agency (Moore, 2016) and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997; Chen, Gully & Eden, 2004)
- Healthy, positive self-concept, and self-esteem (Allison & Von Wald, 2010; Baumeister, Campbell, Krueger, & Vohs, 2003)
- Behavioural patterns and skill sets for transformative competencies, e.g., problem-solving, conflict-resolution, strategic planning, satisfactory social interactions

Depending on the target group and particular program, these are complemented with

- Subject-specific knowledge and technical skills in chosen areas, such as employability or life skills.

The development of a healthy self-concept with good self-esteem, and a reasonable sense of agency and self-efficacy are the subject of much research in OAE (e.g., Cason & Gillis, 1994; Rickinson et al., 2004; Wilson & Lipsey, 2000). In the Edinburgh Model and elsewhere, these are also seen as basis for taking empowered outward actions (Shellman, 2014) on which complex transformative competencies can more easily mature.

3. Structure of the Edinburgh Model

Programs designed using this model feature certain structural elements:

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

- **Three distinct phases** – each with specific elements leading to impact
- **Three underlying principles** that integrate the phases into one continuous process

Empowerment is part of the intended outcomes as well as of the approach to achieve these. The underlying principles support participant growth either directly, in form of active input and interactions, or indirectly, through measures that create a nurturing ground for growth (see Section 4.2). Within this, the phases of the Model are conducted with their specific elements (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Core factors of the Edinburgh Model

The following sections explain these structural elements in detail, along with justifications to their relevance in relation to existing research.

The core of the model covers the time of the actual intervention with the participants. This time is split into three phases (Phase 1-3, described below). For the sake of completeness, it should be said that these three phases are framed by processes of general recruitment or referral ('Phase 0'), and a long-term collaboration with institutions and services that cater to participants after they complete the program ('Phase 4'). Phase 0 and 4 are relevant for positive recruitment and programme completion rates, and integrate the programs into a systems-approach to social services and education. Nevertheless, this paper focusses on the Phases 1 to 3 as they are the ones with direct participant interaction and the facilitation strategies that nurture TCs and empowerment.

Each of the three main phases contains specific elements that lead to the success and impact of the program. They are discussed in the following sections. While an elements may play a valuable role in the other phases as well, they are attributed to the phase in which they are introduced or featured most dominantly.

3.1 Phase 1 – Preparation (Outreach)

Phase 1 is the start of the face-to-face interaction of staff and participants. It focusses on *relationship and trust building* and individual *goal setting* to set a strong foundation for learning and growth.

3.1.1 Relationship and trust building

A trusting relationship is one of the foundational elements of the model, and one that needs to be prioritised at the start of the program. Making an effort to reach out to them in their home contexts

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

and communities is also part of this, as well as transparency concerning objectives, boundaries, and expectations, which affords a predictable framework for the participants to operate in with a sense of orientation, agency, and safety.

3.1.2 Goal setting

In Phase 1, participants are guided to reflect on their personal needs and future ambitions, and formulate goals that they want to work towards during the program. Clear goal setting activates and directs the participants' resources towards gaining the most from the outdoor experience (Phase 2) and consecutive coaching (Phase 3).

The formal objective of phase 1 is to make sure the participants are ready for the outdoor experience in Phase 2, meaning that they (a) have a clear understanding of what to expect from the outdoor phase, and what is expected of them (e.g., basic rules and boundaries) – and that they are willing to adhere to these; and (b) are physically and emotionally in a sufficiently stable condition for spending the days and nights outdoors, personal introspection (e.g. unhindered by addictive behaviours, eating disorders, or self-harming behaviour), and the social interactions. As reaching this readiness is an individual process, the Preparation Phase is somewhat flexible in length and usually includes at least one group session to gauge the social interplay of the participants prior to them launching into the outdoor journey together.

3.2 Phase 2 – Exploration (Wilderness experience)

The central phase consists of a wilderness journey of several days. This can be on foot, by canoe, bike, horse, etc. or with a base camp. The objectives are to enable the participants to experience

- A sense of achievement by mastering physical and socio-emotional challenges
- Convincing evidence of their individual strengths and worthiness
- Tangible effects of their choices and behavioural patterns
- A strong sense of community and cohesion in the group of participants that affords them support and a sense of belonging
- Space for personal reflection and planning of future steps towards lasting change

All of these relate directly to empowerment.

The core part of the model and the format of the second phase is the wilderness experience. For the purpose of the Edinburgh Model 'wilderness' is understood as green and blue spaces with minimal presence of human habitation and infrastructure, as enhanced opportunities to engage with nature and the remoteness of societal interference factors (see below) are conducive to socio-emotional learning (The Wild Foundation, nd.).

3.2.1 Nature

Engaging with natural outdoor environments has significant positive effects on physical and mental health and wellbeing (Capaldi, Dopko, & Zelenski, 2014; WHO, 2016). The Edinburgh Model utilises the benefits of immersion in nature as well as natural encounters as metaphorical 'mirrors' for reflection. Program staff ensure that participants have ample opportunity to become aware of and engage with their immediate natural surroundings through map reading, setting up camp, foraging, contemplation and creative activities to show their value and how they can be incorporated into a daily routine.

3.2.2 Remoteness

Being in wilderness effectively means being remote and separated from the daily commodities and distractions of our home environments and urban infrastructure. Any disruptive relationships (face to

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

face and through social media), addiction temptations, disadvantageous behavioural patterns (e.g., irregular or lack of sleep, eating, hygiene) that might dominate participants' lives at home are suspended during the wilderness phase. This remoteness is amplified by the deliberate abstinence of participants from their mobile phones. Practical experience has found this absence to free resources for introspection, for exploring alternative behaviours that can lead to different social feedback and deeply rooted and sustainable personal change.

3.2.3 Journey

The 'journey' of participants is first and foremost a metaphoric one as they develop over the course of the program. The daily themes and sessions offer a structured guidance for distinct 'steps' along this journey (cf *scaffolding* by Vygotsky). The one-to-one sessions and rotation on leadership roles, and informal group life afford additional opportunities to personalise this path of growth.

Programs can take place ambulant (day activities), residential (at a base camp, hostel, etc.), in form of a physical journey – or a combination of these. While residential courses have their own advantages and merits (Learning Away, nd.; Scrutton, 2020), travelling through the countryside enforces the metaphor of the personal journey by providing constant tangible evidence of change: the landscape, one's levels of fitness, mastery of outdoor skills, etc. This is enhanced by the group setting, where 'travel companions' witness and mirror our transformation.

3.2.4 Daily themes and sessions with self-facilitation tools

These are part of the deliberate facilitation across all phases and will be explained below. While also practiced in other phases, they are most distinct and impactful in Phase 2 as they form a central part of the daily outdoor routine.

All of these factors are geared towards a nurturing ground for growth, plenty of tangible opportunities to practice the elements of empowerment and TCs listed under 1.2, immediate applicability and transferability, and autonomy of the individual.

3.3 Phase 3 – (Re)Integration

The third phase is in the form of coaching to consolidate and expand the learning from the wilderness experience. It offers time and support to integrate newly gained insights, attitudes, and behavioural patterns into the individual context each participant either returns or moves on to. Personal action plans created at the end of the outdoor phase guide the support catered to each participant's needs. Key elements of this phase are the *transfer* of insights and skills gained, and a guided *transition* to a new beginning and onwards trajectory.

3.3.1 Transfer

A well explored shortcoming of many outdoor education programs is the lack of facilitated integration of the experiences and learning from the outdoors to the day-to-day life of the participants in their home, school or work (Sipthorp, Furman, Paisley, Gookin, & Schumann, 2011).

To overcome this setback and even fortify the learning to continue and grow beyond the outdoor phase, staff

- Actively prepare the participants for potential frustrations
- Create a continuation from the outdoors to Phase 3 through smooth handover among staff, address transitions rather than endings, and frequently reconnect to key outdoor memories to reactivate and strengthen personal resources
- Give continued group and one-to-one support to help participants integrate their new self into the old environments

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

This ensures the sustainability of the learning success.

3.3.2 Transitioning onwards

Participants are guided in the process of preparing for departure and independence from the program, and to see their agency and autonomy in taking their growth on a path of their choice. Tangible steps towards this are

- Celebrating achievements, which instils self-worth, pride and motivation to continue
- Highlighting participants' agency and power for self-responsibility
- Helping them to identify a desired and obtainable future for themselves
- Creating an 'action plan' with SMART goals (Doran, 1981) and manageable steps towards them
- Collaborating with other agencies (e.g. job centre, social work, employers) to transition into suitable other courses or services

With often several months in length, Phase 3 is by far the longest in the Edinburgh Model. The exact length is individualised. Engagement of staff fades out as and when individual participants are either taken on by other service providers or autonomously move on.

3.4 Distinct phases *and* continuity

Outdoor experiences in themselves can be valuable for personal growth, yet the conscious processing and reflected learning from that experience is argued to be particularly conducive to generate transferrable insights (Dewey 1938; Ewert & Sibthorp, 2014 ; Seaman & Rheingold, 2013). The practical application of insights and skills gained during the outdoor phase requires time and opportunities. Studies have shown that follow-up events or activities in the home context – such as the sessions in Phase 3 – strongly boost the degree and longevity of learning effects (Furman & Siphthorp, 2013; Leberman & Martin, 2004). The preparatory Phase 1 on the other hand, while less critical for the acquisition of skills and insights, has been noticed to increase the motivation and compliance of the participants before the outdoor phase even starts, and as such is critical for long-term retention and a high completion rate (Venture Trust, nd).

Joining up the three phases smoothly is key to reaping their best effect. Internal evaluation at Venture Trust has shown that the more participants experience the program as one process rather than three separate courses, the stronger the impact and personal change is likely to be. This is achieved primarily by staff communicating the same concepts and self-facilitation tools across all phases, and by being sensitive to specific wording, e.g. when referring to the 'transitioning' between phases rather than 'endings' and new 'beginnings', and 'continuation' of the personal journeys across the program and beyond. This way, the momentum of the learning experience can flow with minimal hindrance and friction. In addition, the phases are woven together by three pedagogical principles that are applied across all phases.

4. Underlying principles across all phases

All decisions and actions taken by program staff are based on the following three principles, so that participants feel supported and smoothly progress along the program.

4.1 Empowerment

The Model applies an *empowerment* approach (compare 2.1), which means that the educators plan and facilitate the learning processes in a way that learners are continually challenged and encouraged to assume responsibility, to reflect critically and to develop their own action plan and initiative so that

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

they can reach their individual aspirations and can become mature and active citizens. The behavior of the educators has this effect either directly, in the form of active inputs and interactions, or indirectly through actions and basic principles that create a nurturing ground for growth.

4.2 A nurturing ground for growth

The setting and interaction processes can support individuals and groups of learners to expand their skills and personal confidence. Such a nurturing ground for growth is seen as a strong contributing factor – if not a condition – for empowerment in group settings. This is in line with established practices of psychotherapy, particularly client-centred therapy (Bozarth & Wilkins, 2001; Rogers 1951), and nested factors of direct and indirect input create and augment this (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Nested factors that create a nurturing ground for socio-emotional learning and growth.

4.3 Deliberate facilitation

Deliberate facilitation aims to achieve the empowerment objective through (a) direct input, and (b) creating a nurturing ground for growth. Key elements and strategies of facilitation are:

4.3.1 Goal-orientation

The clearer and more aware the learning objectives, the more efficient the way to get there, as a general rule. Clear goal-setting is recognised as a major catalyst for learning in formal and non-formal education (Harris, 1998; Hattie, 2009). The course objectives are always at the fore of the pedagogical considerations, and inform the general program design as well as situational decisions of the staff. Routes taken or the speed of travelling and progression of the program are adapted in flexible response to participants' needs.

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

4.3.2 Daily themes and sessions with self-facilitation tools

Every day is set under a specific theme relevant to the course objectives and the participants' backgrounds and needs. They often include:

- Creating a safe space
- Solving problems
- Building appropriate relationships
- Choosing effective behaviours
- Self-evaluation and reviewing
- Transfer, creating a person-specific action plan

These themes are covered in daily group sessions and where situational opportunities arise. The sessions address practical skills and decision-making tools that participants can exercise over the rest of the course, thus increasing their autonomy and self-determination. They are deliberately 'bite-size' and application-oriented so that participants can easily acquire and implement them autonomously – thus promoting their agency and independence as part of the empowerment approach.

4.3.3 Situational micro-learning

Many outdoor activities embed valuable transferrable skills. For example, while participants might find little need at home in knowing how to start a campfire, in order to do so effectively, they need to plan their actions, conduct a situational risk assessment, prepare the required workspace and material, and – depending on the choice of fire-starting method – exercise perseverance. Similarly, a myriad of challenges in the daily routine of outdoor life are utilised for situational learning, and attention is drawn to the transferability of skills and underlying cognitive processes (or 'executive functions', e.g. strategic planning; time, resource, and self-management). The progressive challenges and tangible outcomes from their behaviours and choices help participants acknowledge their agency and self-efficacy. To enhance this, participants are guided in self-reflection and feedback exercises, and small and larger achievements are celebrated for reinforcement.

4.3.4 Combination of individual and group sessions

To enhance individual socio-emotional learning, a group setting is employed. The full group sessions allow participants to benefit from the positive effects of peer support and social cohesion. The peers provide a sounding board, immediate social feedback in a protected setting, and a strong sense of community and belonging. To see that others have similar issues and worries, and how they handle those struggles can be a source of validation and encouragement. The one-to-one sessions on the other hand take place with individual participants and an assigned member of staff as their key worker. Here, conversations focus on personal experiences, struggles and resources, and concrete action plans for change are created and revisited. The personalised space encourages participants to share and reflect on issues they might be less willing to discuss in the group. The combination of group work and one-to-one sessions takes advantages of both approaches, and experience has shown that they enhance each other.

4.3.5 The participant-staff-relationship

A work relationship that bestows trust in the staff is fundamental for the success of the entire program, as participants feel more secure to share personal information, self-reflect, take on feedback and input, and comply with boundaries for participation. This is standard knowledge and professional practice in psychotherapy, and educators can take much guidance from the literature on the *therapeutic alliance* between therapists and clients (Falkenström, Granström, & Holmqvist, 2013). Even in outdoor education it has been shown that strengthening this social foundation right from the

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

start increases the rate of participants completing the program (Conlon, Wilson, Gaffney, & Stoker, 2018), and thereby profiting from its effects.

Therefore, the Edinburgh Model invests in relationship and trust building not just among the group of participants – as is common outdoor education practice to enhance group cohesion (e.g., Martin, Cashel, Wagstaff, & Breunig, 2006) – yet also deliberately between participants and staff.

At the core of this is an ethical stance and philosophy that staff internalise and act on. It is expressed in a benign openness and non-judgmental demeanour towards every single participant. Showing genuine interest in their individual needs, worries, and talents, and treating – even what are usually considered ‘undesirable’ – behaviours as participants’ current autonomous choice, communicates respect and enforces their agency and self-worth (cf *unconditional positive regard* by Rogers, 1951; See also Bozarth & Wilkins, 2001). Glasser’s (1998) *Choice Theory* lends itself as one of the self-facilitation tools for this purpose.

4.3.6 Safe space

As previously indicated, participants need to feel physically and socio-emotionally safe in order to free resources for self-reflection and experimentation with new behavioural patterns (Davis-Berman & Berman, 2002; Leberman & Martin, 2003). A *safe space* is developed on an explicit or tacit social agreement to respect and protect each other from harm, and can effectively promote group cohesion and peer support (Hildmann & Hardie, 2019).

5. The Edinburgh Model in practice and research

Models are simplification of processes and interrelations designed for and deducted from real life. The key elements of the Edinburgh Model can be implemented in a variety of ways, and in combination with different learning foci and target groups. To show the variability of the model, we present a few examples of different courses to illustrate how the model is being used already, followed by insights gained so far on how it can be adapted to new contexts and target groups.

5.1 Example applications of the Edinburgh Model

The following are existing programs that exemplify the diversity of the Model in practice.

5.1.1 Inspiring Young Futures

This course caters for young people between 16 and 25 years of age with some kind of experience with the social care system. The primary objective is to enable the participants to gauge where and how they can exert agency in their life, and to develop the strategic and social skills to navigate social interactions to their satisfaction. Phase 1 consists of approx. 6 individual and one group session, the Phase 2 wilderness experience is 8 days in length, and the coaching during Phase 3 takes up to 6 months. The basic quantitative criterion for success is whether the participants return to some form of education, training or employment upon program completion. Next to this, evidence of increased sense of agency and self-worth, healthy behavioural routines and constructive life choices are primary course objectives.

5.1.2 Positive Futures

The Positive Futures program is designed for people who have served in military forces struggling to re-integrate into civilian society. Objectives are lifestyle stabilisation, ‘functioning’ in social contexts, identifying individual coping mechanisms and behaviour triggers, and achieving positive life changes. The 7-day wilderness experience focusses on communal living and healthy routines. Cognitive

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

behavioural approaches (e.g., reality therapy, choice theory) create a therapeutic environment appropriate to and effective with stress and mental health issues typical for army veterans (Gap, 2018).

5.1.3 From Outdoors to Labour Market (FOLM)

This European project implements the Edinburgh Model in three European regions to reduce youth unemployment. The three regional participant groups vary in terms of level of education, socio-cultural parameters, available infrastructure, and labour market conditions. For example, Cantabria, Northern Spain, targets university graduates struggling to find employment in a crisis-stricken labour market. A local culture of adults still living with parents, and financial benefits for the unemployed discourage efforts to reach employment (e.g. willingness to commute). In the Mid-West of Ireland on the other hand, most participants come from multiple deprived backgrounds that significantly impede personal and social skills as well as access to the labour market. All participating regions have successfully adopted the Edinburgh Model with modifications responding to geographical, cultural and political conditions.

5.2 Research evidence on the Edinburgh Model

The Edinburgh Model deliberately incorporates factors widely evidenced to promote SEL in outdoor and experiential learning contexts (see section 2). In addition, several studies have focused specifically on programs following the Edinburgh Model.

5.2.1 Program evaluation at the Venture Trust

The four main programs offered by Venture Trust all follow the Edinburgh Model, have run for several years, and have undergone several review phases and formal evaluations (Table 1).

(Current) Program title	Participant group	Years running	Evaluations
Living Wild	Adults on Community Payback Orders or with criminal record	2007–present	The Venture Trust (nd).
Inspiring Young Futures	Young people (age 16–24) with experience of social care	2009–present	Between The Lines (2019); CELCIS (2013)
Next Steps	Women at risk of offending or re-offending	2010–present	Mitchell, Westphal, & Higgins (2012); SMCI Associates (2018)
Positive Futures	Army veterans struggling with civilian life	2016–present	Gap Communications (2018)

Table 1. Programs following the Edinburgh Model at the Venture Trust

5.2.2 From Outdoors To Labour Market

The evaluation of the FOLM project (2018-2022) is led by the University of Edinburgh and combines qualitative and quantitative research methods. Preliminary findings show a success rate of around 80% (depending on region) of getting participants into employment, training or education and significant increase in indicators of TCs (FOLM Consortium, in prep).

5.3 Practical implementation

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

Wherever models are applied in practice, certain local and organisational determinants occur. Minor or major adaptations are required with every group of individuals to tailor a program for their maximum gain and growth. As long as decisions on facilitation and intervention options are made with the underlying principles (see 4) and person/group-specific learning objectives in mind, the Edinburgh Model has shown to be widely adaptable without forfeiting its benefits. Much rather, being responsive to group and context factors is likely to increase the effectiveness of this – and maybe any – program design.

5.3.1 Socio-cultural adaptation

Some of the context factors can be geographical and socio-cultural. The Edinburgh Model is evidenced to successfully translate transnationally (FOLM Consortium, in prep.) Some of the challenges requiring adaptations in a new geographic or cultural setting include

- Socio-cultural and other barriers or enablers (e.g., political ‘climate’, legislation, prevalent ideologies, class system, role of religion and/or mysticism)
- Heritage, including sociological and cultural connection to nature, wilderness, and place
- Educational relationships (power hierarchy, social norms, level of formality, permission to question, etc.)
- Gender-related issues (e.g. balance of power in gendered relationships, social rules, respect, gendered conceptions of authority)

Considering and integrating these in the program implementation can significantly increase the compliance and completion rate of participants, synergies with existing resources, and a smooth forward transition at the end of the program.

5.3.2 Combination with additional theories and models

Where an organisation or staff have positive experience and expertise with additional educational or therapeutic approaches, they might be inclined to merge these with the Edinburgh Model. For example, the authors and their teams have found philosophical elements and practical tools of the following to integrate well with the Edinburgh Model and enhance participants’ growth and TCs:

- Choice theory (Glasser, 1998)
- Transactional analysis (Berne, 2015)
- Systems theory/approach (Senge, 2016; See also Ewert & Sibthorp, 2014)
- Narrative approach (Cassidi, 2001; Willis, 2011)
- Growth mindset (Dweck, 2017) and grit (Duckworth, 2016)

All of these also lend themselves for the thematic sessions as easy to grasp concepts that create a common language among the learning community, and that provide clear and simple self-facilitation tools for the participants.

6. Conclusions

Outdoor Adventure Education programmes are widely evidenced to promote SEL and competencies that are strongly associated with transformative learning and empowerment. Professional associations and academics have endorsed this and emphasize the socio-political potential of outdoor and experiential learning to make a significant contribution towards increased citizenship and personal transformation.

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

This paper presents a programme model that has been evidenced in a number of studies to achieve this by effectively and sustainably increasing core components of TCs and empowerment in their participants. The examples of existing programs demonstrate the versatility of the model with a range of target groups and in different regional and cultural contexts. Research into the potential boundaries of the model's flexibility are currently under way, and future studies could isolate confounding factors or evaluate the benefits of combining the model with related approaches (as listed under 3.3).

The authors envision that sharing this model will enable practitioners and program designers to incorporate elements to enhance existing programs and/or to employ the model in whole to facilitate transformative outdoor learning experiences that equip participants with the competencies and frames of reference critical for individual wellbeing and life satisfaction while also enabling them to exert their rights and responsibilities as national and global citizens towards peaceful and prosperous societies – including the more-than-human systems and ecosystems we are part of.

References

- Allison, P., & Von Wald, K. (2010). Exploring values in the wilderness: Personal and social development on educational expeditions. *Pastoral Care in Education, 28*(3), 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02643944.2010.504222>
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: Freeman & Co.
- Baumeister, R. F., Campbell, J. D., Krueger, J. I., & Vohs, K. D. (2003). Does high self-esteem cause better performance, interpersonal success, happiness, or healthier lifestyles? *Psychological Science in the Public Interest, 4*, 1–44.
- Beard, C., & Wilson, J. P. (2009). *Experiential Learning. A best practice handbook for educators and trainers*. 2nd ed. London, UK & Philadelphia, PA: Kogan Page.
- Berman, D. S. & Davis-Berman, J. (2005). Positive psychology and outdoor education. *Journal of Experiential Education, 28*(1), 17–24. Doi: [10.1177/105382590502800104](https://doi.org/10.1177/105382590502800104)
- Berne, E. (2015). *Transactional analysis in psychotherapy. A systematic individual and social psychiatry*. Reprint of the 1961 edition.
- Between The Lines. (2019). *Inspiring Young Futures program evaluation 2016-2019. Third year report*.
- Bozarth, J. & Wilkins, P. (2001). *Roger's therapeutic conditions: Evolution, theory and practice. Unconditional positive regard. Vol. 3* Monmouth, UK: PCCS Books.
- Broom, C. (2015). Empowering students: Pedagogy that benefits educators and learners. *Citizenship, Social and Economics Education, 14*(2), 79-86. DOI: [10.1177/2047173415597142](https://doi.org/10.1177/2047173415597142)
- Capaldi, C. A., Dopko, R. L., & Zelenski, J. M. (2014). The relationship between nature connectedness and happiness. A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology, 5*. Doi: [10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00976](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00976)
- Cason, D., & Gillis, H.L. (1994). A meta-analysis of outdoor adventure programming with adolescents. *Journal of Experiential Education, 17*(1), 40–47.
- Cassidi, K. (2001). Enhancing your experiential program with narrative theory. *Journal of Experiential Education, 24*(1), 22–26. Doi: [10.1177/105382590102400106](https://doi.org/10.1177/105382590102400106)
- Cattaneo, L. B., & Chapman, A. R. (2010). The process of empowerment: A model for use in research and practice. *American Psychologist, 65*, 646–659.

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

- CELCIS. (2013). Inspiring Young Futures. Evaluation of the Venture Trust's Inspiring Young Futures (IYF) Program. Retrieved from www.celcis.org
- Chase, D.L. (2015). Does Challenge by Choice increase participation? *Journal of Experiential Education*, 38(2), 108–128. Doi: 10.1177/1053825914524057
- Chen, G., Gully, S.M., & Eden, D. (2004). General self-efficacy and self-esteem: Toward theoretical and empirical distinction between correlated self-evaluations. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 25, 375–395. Doi: 10.1002/job.251
- Conlon, C. M., Wilson, C. E., Gaffney, P., & Stoker, M. (2018). Wilderness therapy intervention with adolescents: Exploring the process of change. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 18(4), 353–366. Doi: 10.1080/14729679.2018.1474118
- Davis-Berman, J. & Berman, D. (2002). Risk and anxiety in adventure programming. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 25(2), 305–310. Doi: [10.1177/105382590202500209](https://doi.org/10.1177/105382590202500209)
- Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education*. Kappa Delta Pi. New York, NY: Simon & Schuster.
- Doran, G. T. (1981). There's a S.M.A.R.T. way to write management's goals and objectives. *Management Review*, 70(11), 35–36.
- Duckworth, A. (2016). *Grit. The power of passion and perseverance*. New York, NY: Simon & Schuster.
- Dweck, C. (2017). *Mindset. Changing the way you think to fulfil your potential*. London, UK: Robinson.
- Ewert, A.W., & Sibthorp, J. (2014). *Outdoor Adventure Education. Foundations, Theory, and Research*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Falkenström, F., Granström, F., & Holmqvist, R. (2013). Therapeutic alliance predicts symptomatic improvement session by session. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 60(3), 317–328. Doi: 10.1037/a0032258
- FOLM Consortium. (in prep). Preliminary research findings.
- Furman, N., & Siphthorp, J. (2013). Leveraging experiential learning techniques for learning. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 137, 17–26.
- Gap Communications. (2018). Evaluation of the 'Positive Futures' Program 2016–2018 for veterans struggling with civilian life. Retrieved from https://50ca3b8f-d6ee-4332-91cf-0330d1510970.filesusr.com/ugd/9df89b_eb558abca15f4c869337e40e3a59ec30.pdf
- Glasser, W. (1998). *Choice theory: A new psychology of personal freedom*. New York, NY: Harper Perennial.
- Harris, A. (1998). Effective teaching: A review of the literature. *School Leadership & Management*, 18(2), 169–183. Doi: 10.1080/13632439869628
- Hattie, J. A. C. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Abingdon-on-Thames, UK: Routledge.
- Hildmann, J., & Hardie, A. (2019). *The importance of a 'safe space' to encourage participation*. Paper presented at the 18th Conference of the European Institute Outdoor, Adventure, and Experiential Learning. Tralee, Ireland, September 24–27.
- Learning Away. (n.d.). What makes a brilliant residential? Retrieved from <http://learningaway.org.uk/thecampaign/what-makes-a-brilliant-residential/>

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

- Leberman, S. A. & Martin, A. J. (2003). Does pushing comfort zones produce peak learning experiences? *Australian Journal of Outdoor Education*, 7(1), 10–19.
- Leberman, S. I. & Martin, A. J. (2004). Enhancing transfer of learning through post-course reflection. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 4(2), 173–184.
- Lloyd, J. A. (2018). *Evaluation of the Positive Futures program 2016–2018*. Edinburgh & Glasgow, UK: Venture Trust.
- Martin, B., Cashel, C., Wagstaff, M., & Breunig, M. (2006). *Outdoor Leadership. Theory and Practice*, Ch. 10, pp 133–147. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Mitchell, F., Westphal, R., & Higgins, P. (2012). *An evaluation of Venture Trust's 'Next Steps' program. Final report*. Edinburgh, UK: The University of Edinburgh.
- Moore, J. W. (2006). What is the sense of agency and why does it matter? *Frontiers in Psychology*. 7:1272. Doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01272
- OECD / Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2005). *The definition and selection of key competencies: Executive summary*. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/pisa/35070367.pdf>
- OECD. (2019). OECD Future of Education and skills 2030: Thought Leader written statement. Retrieved from [http://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/teaching-and-learning/learning/transformative-competencies/Thought leader written statement Rychen.pdf](http://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/teaching-and-learning/learning/transformative-competencies/Thought%20leader%20written%20statement%20Rychen.pdf).
- Rickinson, M., Dillon, J., Teamey, K., Morris, M., Choi, M.Y., Sanders, D., & Benefield, P. (2004). A review of research on outdoor learning. Published by the National Foundation for Educational Research and King's College London.
- Rogers, C. R. (1951). *Client-centred therapy. Its current practice, implications, and theory*. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.
- Russell, K. C., Hendee, J. C., & Phillips-Miller, D. (2000). How wilderness therapy works: An examination of the wilderness therapy process to treat adolescents with behavioral problems and addictions. *USDA Forest Service Proceedings RMRS-P-15*, Vol. 3, 207–217.
- Scrutton, R. (2020). Investigating the process of learning for school pupils on residential outdoor education courses. *Journal of Outdoor and Environmental Education* 23, 39–56. Doi: 10.1007/s42322-019-00044-4
- Seaman, J. & Rheingold, A. (2013). Circle talks as situated experiential learning: Context, identity, and knowledgeability in 'Learning from Reflection'. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 36(2), 155–174. Doi: 10.1177/1053825913487887
- Senge, P. M. (2016). *The fifth discipline. The art & practice of the learning organisation*. 2nd ed. London, UK: Random House.
- Shellman, A. (2014). Empowerment and Experiential Education: A state of knowledge paper. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 37(1), 18–30.
- Sipthorp, J., Furman, N., Paisley, K., Gookin, J., & Schumann, S. (2011). Mechanisms of Learning Transfer in Adventure Education: Qualitative Results from the NOLS Transfer Survey. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 34(2), 109–126.
- SMCI Associates. (2018). 'Next Steps' Program evaluation 2014-2017. Report to Venture Trust. Retrieved from https://50ca3b8f-d6ee-4332-91cf-0330d1510970.filesusr.com/ugd/9df89b_9ee7b6a647024d209121be39f1a70223.pdf

Empowerment and transformative competencies through socio-emotional learning in the outdoors – the Edinburgh Model

The Wild Foundation (nd). Retrieved from <https://wild.org/>

Tuckman, B. W., & Jensen, M. A. C. (1977). Stages of small-group development revisited. *Group & Organization Management*, 2(4), 419–427.

UN / United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs Sustainable Development. (n.d.). Sustainable Development Goals. Retrieved from <https://sdgs.un.org/>

UNESCO. (2015). Transversal competencies in education policy and practice. Regional synthesis report, Phase I. Retrieved from <https://transversalcompetencies.weebly.com/uploads/2/8/4/2/28422343/transversal.pdf>

Venture Trust. (n.d.). Internal data and reports. Unpublished.

WHO / World Health Organisation. (2016). *Urban green spaces and health. A review of evidence*. WHO Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Willis, A. (2011). Re-storying wilderness and adventure therapies: healing places and selves in an era of environmental crises. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 11(2), 91–108. doi: [10.1080/14729679.2011.633375](https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2011.633375)

Wilson, S. J., Lipsey, M. W. (2000). Wilderness challenge programs for delinquent youth: a meta-analysis of outcome evaluations. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 23, 1–12.